

ISSUES OF MUSEUMIFICATION OF INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE OBJECTS

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Abstract: This article studies samples of the intangible cultural heritage of Uzbekistan and the problems of their preservation for the future generation. Regulatory documents on the protection of intangible cultural heritage were also analyzed and issues of their promotion with the help of museums were considered. The causes of these problems have also been investigated.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, UNESCO, representative list, intangible cultural heritage, law, declaration, factor, national value, tradition, museum, program.

Museumification is a direction of museum activity that involves transforming heritage into objects of museum display. The museumification of intangible heritage assumes its consolidation into tangible carriers and its further implementation. The actualization of an intangible object is carried out within the framework of exhibitions and cultural-educational events.

There are various methods of museumification of intangible heritage objects, including conservation, actualization, and museumification:

1. Conservation: This involves preserving an intangible heritage object by removing it from its existing environment and storing it within museum collections using tangible means. In such cases, intangible objects are recorded through video or audio recordings, ethnographic descriptions, and are included in museum archives or documentary funds.

2. Actualization: This method entails integrating the museum object into a contemporary environment or museum space. Actualization is particularly important in the museumification of intangible heritage, as traditions need to be continuously repeated to remain relevant.

3. Museumification: This approach allows the preservation and development of an intangible heritage object in its active state. This involves preserving a tradition in a museum space in a way that mirrors its natural historical and cultural environment, while incorporating adaptive mechanisms.

In the 20th century, with the acceleration of globalization processes across all fields, many forms of intangible culture faced the threat of being forgotten and lost. Consequently, the identification and preservation of intangible (spiritual) heritage as an integral part of global cultural heritage have become

pressing issues for modern scientific communities.

At the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries, the problem of preserving intangible heritage objects came to the forefront due to the risk of losing many cultural forms vital to human self-identification. The museumification of intangible cultural heritage is becoming increasingly important, requiring in-depth development of preservation and presentation strategies. According to E. N. Mastenitsa, the integration of intangible heritage issues into the theoretical and practical interests of museum hermeneutics not only influences the methods of museum work and the development of exhibition and interpretation practices but also contributes to the emergence of new types of museums, such as eco-museums and living museums.

Intangible cultural heritage refers to traditions, expressions, knowledge, and skills—along with related instruments, objects, artifacts, and cultural spaces—that communities, groups, and individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage. Its essence lies in its transmission and acceptance by living people, often referred to as “living heritage” in academic discourse.

The initial stage of forming a system for preserving intangible heritage can be traced back to 1973, when the Bolivian government requested UNESCO to develop model proposals for the regulation, development, and dissemination of folklore. The term “intangible heritage” emerged in the late 20th century in modern humanities, leading to an expansion of museum boundaries and a shift in the scientific paradigm of museology.

Ivo Maroević broadened the interpretation of "heritage," emphasizing the transition in the concept of heritage in museology. According to him, the European model of museum institutions, which began during the Renaissance and culminated in the 1980s, was primarily focused on collecting, preserving, and exhibiting material world values. However, he argued that intangible heritage extends beyond the scope of museological theory. He also highlighted the role of museums and museologists in preserving and displaying intangible heritage as a part of social identity.

In 2003, UNESCO adopted the "Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage," which includes customs, performances, expressions, knowledge, and skills, along with associated objects and cultural spaces. Today, UNESCO implements measures to protect intangible heritage, including developing the "Declaration of Masterpieces of Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity." According to this declaration, intangible heritage is defined as:

- A collection of traditional creative expressions reflecting a community's social and cultural identity.

- Standards and values passed down orally or through other means.

In Uzbekistan, the 2003 UNESCO "Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage" was ratified in 2008. Between 1993 and 2020, Uzbekistan nominated five tangible cultural heritage objects and eight intangible cultural heritage items to the UNESCO World Heritage List, with plans to nominate over ten tangible and five intangible cultural heritage objects by 2030.

The following forms of intangible cultural heritage are preserved in Uzbekistan:

Oral traditions and expressions, including language as a carrier of intangible cultural heritage.

Performing arts, including acting, musical performance, singing, and dancing.

Customs, rituals, and festive events.

Knowledge and practices related to nature and the universe.

Traditional craftsmanship and associated knowledge and skills.

Since independence, Uzbekistan has adopted special laws and developed state programs to preserve cultural heritage. These regulatory documents create a foundation for safeguarding the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people and passing it on to future generations. State programs also emphasize the development of international cooperation in preserving cultural heritage [6] .

The concept of intangible heritage encompasses the social mechanism of transmitting traditions. Museums play a vital role in preserving intangible heritage. When it is impossible to preserve intangible heritage objects in their natural socio-cultural environment, they can be museumified. Museum professionals have drawn attention to issues surrounding intangible heritage, defining and classifying it, and establishing methods for working with it in museums.

According to I.A. Chuklinova, French scholars A. Devallée, B. Deloche, J. Davallon, and F. Méro were among the first to focus on identifying and studying elements of intangible heritage that could be museumified, adhering to advanced views on the natural and cultural environment of humanity [7] .

Understanding intangible heritage is primarily linked to issues of preserving and interpreting tangible cultural heritage. Before analyzing the place of intangible heritage objects in museum work, they must be identified as

museum items. Clearly, envisioning the ideal representation of an object in a museum is challenging. To avoid such problems, it is essential to preserve the object in its traditional form.

When asked, “What happens to intangible heritage objects when they become museum items?” the answer lies in the fact that such objects cannot simply be displayed, restored, or exhibited as tangible items. In the museumification method, the process and conditions of the object's emergence are museumified rather than the object itself.

Like tangible heritage objects, intangible cultural heritage objects contribute to increasing the number of tourists visiting a country. This is because cultural and social characteristics significantly influence the attractiveness of a tourist destination for various groups and categories of visitors. Many tourists are interested in a nation's culture, art, science, religion, and history. The musical potential of a region is one of the most captivating elements of its culture. In some countries, music serves as the main factor attracting tourists. Renowned music festivals bring together thousands of participants annually [8] .

One of Uzbekistan's traditional events is the Sharq Taronalari International Music Festival, which plays a significant role in promoting classical music and national melodies.

Uzbekistan's updated national list of intangible cultural heritage includes over 60 nominations across five categories. Additionally, objects such as Kobiz Performance have been listed under UNESCO's Urgent Safeguarding List of Intangible Cultural Heritage. Five other elements, including Bakhshi Art, Ethnosport, Woodcarving Art, Halfachilik, and Uzbek Martial Arts, have been added to UNESCO's Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. Furthermore, the Rishton Ceramics School has been recommended for UNESCO's Register of Best Practices in Intangible Cultural Heritage.

Today, museum professionals pay significant attention to intangible heritage objects. One of their primary tasks is to analyze and preserve certain cultural treasures that are at risk of extinction and trace their deep roots. According to generalized data, the representation and status of intangible heritage objects in museums depend on their domestic character and preservation level. In some cases, representatives of traditions themselves can become “museum objects.”

Indeed, the classification of intangible heritage objects within museums is based on the method used during their museumification. Classifying objects by

their type is another fundamental principle of this system.

In conclusion, intangible cultural heritage objects encompass a wide range, from everyday life to traditional culture and art, including their history and context. Efforts to immortalize intangible heritage are being actively carried out by experts and museum professionals. In addition to preserving and displaying historical and cultural items, museums also safeguard and disseminate socially significant information through such objects. UNESCO's International Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage, adopted in Paris in 2003, serves as both the outcome of intensive scholarly discussions and a guide for action.

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